

Bismuth(III)-selective membrane electrode based on inorganic ion exchanger

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Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) based membrane electrodes of antimony(III) silicate were prepared using different plasticizing materials like dibutyl phthalate (DBP), dioctylphthalate (DOP), dibutyl(butyl)phosphonate (DBBP) as plasticizers and sodium tetraphenylborate (NaTPB) as plasticizing solvent mediator and 1-chloronaphthalene (CN) as an anion excluder for Bi³⁺ selective sensors. The inorganic ion exchanger based membrane electrode exhibits linearity over a wide concentration range of 2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ with a slope of 29.6 mV decade⁻¹ of activity. The electrode assembly works between pH 2.0–7.0, exhibits a fast response time of 20 s and performs satisfactorily over a period of two months with good reproducibility. Excellent selectivity of the order of 10⁻³ over a number of cations and quantitative determination of bismuth(III) in pharmaceutical preparations demonstrates the utility of the proposed sensor.

Since ever the successful use in the treatment of syphilis¹, bismuth has been extended its pharmaceutical uses in anti-acids, peptic ulcer treatment and topical dermatological creams. Simultaneously, there is a necessity to determine bismuth contents in pharmaceutical preparations mainly for its control in treatment of patients with gastrointestinal disease.

Several analytical methods such as X-ray fluorescence spectrometry², electrochemical atomic absorption spectrometry (ETAAS)³, hydride generation-electrochemical atomic absorption spectrometry (HG-ETAAS) with *in situ* preconcentration⁴, inductively coupled plasma (ICP)-mass spectrometry^{5,6}, ICP-AES⁷ are widely used for the determination of bismuth in biological and pharmaceutical materials. However, most of these equipments are very expensive. In recent years, potentiometric membrane sensors have been widely used in pharmaceutical analysis⁸⁻¹⁰. This is mainly due to simple design, low cost, adequate selectivity, low detection limit, high accuracy, wide concentration range and applicability of the selective electrodes to colored and turbid solutions.

The present work describes a simple potentiometric PVC-membrane sensor for the determination of bismuth(III) in pharmaceutical preparations. In continuation of our work⁹, the use of an ion exchanger as an active component for the membranes has been investigated and the results are presented herein.

Results and discussion

Working concentration range : The potential response of all the membrane sensors was studied in the concentration range 1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ Bi³⁺. Ion exchanger based membrane without solvent mediator (electrode no. 1) exhibited linearity in the concentration range 1.0×10^{-4} – 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ with a slope of 26.0 mV decade⁻¹ of activity. The potentials generated across these membranes are ascribed to uptake bismuth ions on ion exchangers. Plasticizers are frequently used to enhance the response characteristics, i.e. working concentration range, slope etc. The effect of addition of plasticizers to the membrane was, therefore, studied and significant improvement with regard to working concentration range and slope was observed. Addition of solvent mediators DBP and DBBP improved the performance of inorganic ion exchanger based membrane, exhibiting a working concentration range of 2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ with slopes of 28.5 mV decade⁻¹ of activity (electrode no. 2). The addition of solvent mediator (NaTPB) and anion excluder (CN) had no significant improvement in the performance of the electrode. Repeated monitoring of potentials on the same portions of the sample gave a standard deviation of ± 0.3 mV. The standard deviation of the slope was ± 0.8 mV, which shows good reproducibility of the electrode assembly.

Response and lifetime :

The response time of the membranes without solvent mediators was found to be approximately 60 s. The addition of solvent mediators improved the response time significantly with the best results shown by electrode no. 2 (20 s) (Table 1) over the entire concentration range, the potentials remain constant for more than 5 min. Membrane electrode no. 2 was henceforth selected for further studies. The membrane could be used over a period of two months without observing significant change in slope and response time and this could be corrected by re-equilibrating the membrane with $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ Bi}^{3+}$ solution for 2–3 days. During usage, they were stored in $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ Bi}^{3+}$ solution.

pH and non-aqueous effect :

The pH dependence of the membrane sensor (electrode no. 2) has been investigated at 1.0×10^{-2} and $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ Bi}^{3+}$ ions and the pH of the solutions were adjusted by the addition of HNO_3 or NaOH . It is found that potentials remain steady between pH 2.0–7.0 and consequently, the same may be taken as valid pH range of the projected sensor. The sharp change in potentials below 2.0 and above pH 7.0 may be due to H^+ ion co-fluxing and hydrolysis of Bi^{3+} ions, respectively. In order to assess the performance of the sensor in partially non-aqueous medium, its functioning was studied in methanol-water, ethanol-water and acetone-water mixtures and

the results are tabulated in Table 2. It is observed that the performance of the electrode is satisfactory in non-aqueous solution containing up to 50% partially non-aqueous content, as the working concentration ranges do not change considerably. However, these values reduce significantly when the non-aqueous content exceeds this concentration ($> 50\% \text{ v/v}$).

Potentiometric selectivity coefficients :

The selectivity coefficients of the proposed membrane selective electrode were determined against a number of interfering ions using the separate solution method¹⁰ with fixed $10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of both bismuth and interferant ions. The obtained data (Table 3) show that the sensor exhibits good selectivity coefficient values for bismuth ions over the most of tested common species.

Determination of bismuth contents in pharmaceutical drugs :

The determination of bismuth contents in the pharmaceutical mixtures, by proposed bismuth(III)-selective membrane electrode based on antimony(III) silicate and the use of EDTA as a tritrant¹¹ was successfully applied. Table 4 shows the results obtained for bismuth(III) determination using potentiometric and atomic absorption spectroscopy methods. The results are in good agreements and are within an acceptable range of error ($< 2\text{--}4\%$), indicating that electrode can be utilized for a determination of Bi^{III} in various samples.

Table 1. Composition and response characteristics of PVC based antimony(III) silicate membranes selective for Bi^{3+} ions

Electrode/ membrane no.	% (w/w) of various components							Working concn. range (mol dm^{-3})	Slope mV decade^{-1} of activity	Response time, s
	Ion exchanger	DBP	DOP	DBBP	CN	NaTPB	PVC			
1	10	5	–	5	5	–	75	1.0×10^{-4} – 1.0×10^{-1}	26.0	60
2	10	25	–	5	5	5	50	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	28.5	20
3	10	5	25	5		5	45	3.6×10^{-5} – 1.0×10^{-1}	34.0	28
4	10	10	10	25	5	5	35	5.6×10^{-5} – 1.0×10^{-1}	29.6	35
5	10	10	10	10	25	5	30	1.0×10^{-5} – 1.0×10^{-1}	35.3	40

Table 2. Performance of bismuth(III) selective PVC based-antimony(III) silicate membrane electrode (electrode no. 2) in non-aqueous medium

Non aqueous content % (v/v)	Working concentration range (mol dm^{-3})		
	Acetone	Ethanol	Methanol
10	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}
20	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}
30	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}
40	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}
50	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}
60	3.23×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	4.32×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}	3.37×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-1}

Table 3. Selectivity coefficient values resulting [$K^{Pot}_{Bi^{3+},B}$] values for Bi^{3+} -selective sensors (electrode no. 2)

Interfering ion, B	Selectivity coefficients, $K^{Pot}_{Bi^{3+},B}$	Interfering ion, B	Selectivity coefficients, $K^{Pot}_{Bi^{3+},B}$
NH_4^+	2.4×10^{-3}	Co^{2+}	3.7×10^{-3}
Na	2.5×10^{-3}	Ni^{2+}	2.9×10^{-3}
K^+	3.9×10^{-3}	Cd^{2+}	1.5×10^{-3}
Tl^+	3.0×10^{-3}	Pb^{2+}	3.9×10^{-3}
Cs^+	2.9×10^{-3}	Hg^{2+}	2.5×10^{-3}
Cu^{2+}	4.8×10^{-3}	Mn^{2+}	2.2×10^{-3}
Ca^{2+}	3.8×10^{-3}	Fe^{3+}	3.6×10^{-3}
Sr^{2+}	1.0×10^{-3}	Al^{3+}	4.1×10^{-3}
Ba^{2+}	3.0×10^{-3}	Ce^{3+}	3.2×10^{-3}
Mg^{2+}	3.6×10^{-3}		

Table 4. Comparison of determination of Bi^{III} in different stomach anti-acids using bismuth(III) selective PVC based-antimony(III) silicate membrane electrode and atomic absorption spectrometry

Sl. no.	Drug	Amount of drug	Potentiometric method		AAS method	
			Recovery ^a	RSD (%)	Recovery	RSD (%)
1.	Bismuth oxonitrate ($BiONO_3$)	0.25	98.45	0.89	99.13	0.65
	Kaolin	0.25				
2.	Bismuth oxonitrate ($BiONO_3$)	0.38	99.48	1.12	99.44	0.77
	Magnesium carbonate ($MgCO_3$)	0.43				
	Sodium bicarbonate ($NaHCO_3$)	0.25				
	Rutin ($C_{27}H_{30}O_{16}$)	0.02				

^aAll values were the average of three determinations.

Experimental

Synthesis of an inorganic ion exchanger, antimony(III) silicate was done as reported earlier¹². High relative molecular weight PVC (Fluka, Zurich), antimony(III) chloride and sodium silicate (B.D.H., India), tetrahydrofuran (THF) (Loba Chemicals), sodium tetraphenylborate (NaTPB) (Poole, Dorset, UK), dibutylphthalate (DBP) and dioctylphthalate (DOP) from Reidel (India), dibutyl(butyl)phosphonate (DBBP) from Mobil (Richmond, USA) and 1-chloronaphthalene (CN) from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) were used without further purification. Organic solvents were purified by distillation and solutions of metal nitrates (Merck) were prepared in double distilled water.

Preparation and fabrication of membrane electrodes :

The PVC-based membranes were prepared by the method of Craggs *et al.*¹³. Varying amounts of the ion-active phase (ion exchanger) and an appropriate amount

of PVC were dissolved in 20 ml THF. The anion excluder (CN), solvent mediator (NaTPB) and different plasticizers (DBP, DOP, DBBP) and were also added in some cases to get membranes of different compositions (Table 1). The solution thus obtained, after complete dissolution of the various components, was poured into glass rings placed on a smooth glass plate and allowed to evaporate at room temperature. After 48 h, transparent membranes of 0.5 mm thickness were obtained. The so obtained thin membrane was cut in the shapes of discs of about 2 cm diameter and fixed at the one end of the glass tube with the help of araldite. Finally the assembly was allowed to dry in air for 24 h. The glass-tube was filled with 0.01 M solution of the ion towards which the membrane is selective and kept dipped in an identical solution of the same ion at room temperature. The membrane electrode then fabricated was preconditioned in a 0.01 M solution of the appropriate electrolyte for at least 24 h before use. The ratio of membrane ingredients, time of contact and con-

centration of equilibrating solution were optimized so that the membranes produce reproducible, noiseless and stable potentials. Membrane to membrane reproducibility was assured by carefully following the optimum conditions of fabrication. Composition of the membranes, which gave best performance, is listed in Table 1.

Potential measurements :

All emf measurements were carried out with the following assembly, Ag-AgCl, 0.01 mol dm⁻³ KCl/internal solution (0.01 mol dm⁻³ Bi³⁺)/PVC/membrane/test solution/Ag-AgCl, 3 mol dm⁻³ KCl.

A model 692 Metrohm ion analyzer pH/mV meter was used for the potential measurements 25.0 ± 0.1°C. Single junction Ag-AgCl reference electrodes were used. All measurements were carried out in a 50 mL double walled glass cell, with constant magnetic stirring of the test solution.

Direct potentiometric determination of bismuth in pharmaceutical substances¹¹ :

About 0.5 g of different stomach anti-acids tablets (Table 4) were dissolved in 5 mL of concentrated nitric acid by heating to decoloration, filtered and diluted to 50 mL with deionized water. After that, 25 mL of Na₄EDTA solution was transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask and this volume was completed with the deionized water. Now, the solution was used for the determination of Bi^{III} by proposed bismuth(III) selective PVC based-antimony(III) silicate membrane electrode.

References

1. R. R. Catterson, G. G. Duggin, J. S. Horvath and D. J. Tiller, *Aust. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1978, **7**, 111.
2. R. N. Galante, J. C. Egoville, A. J. Visalli and D. M. Patel, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1981 **70**, 167.
3. P. M. Belanger, M. Lalande, F. Dore and G. Labrecque, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1983, **72**, 1092.
4. G. Guidi, D. Olzer, R. Schiavon and M. Zatti, *Clin. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **131**, 325.
5. R. A. Brandon, M. J. Eadie and M. T. Smith, *Ther. Drug Monit.*, 1995, **7**, 216.
6. J. Klimes, J. Sochor, M. Zahradnicek and J. Sedlacek, *J. Chromatogr. Biomed. Appl.*, 1992, **122**, 221.
7. C. N. Ou and V. L. Fraley, *Clin. Chem.*, 1982, **28**, 2157.
8. Z. Z. Zhang and V. V. Cosofret, *Electrode Rev.*, 1990, **12**, 35; V. V. Cosofret and R. P. Buck, "Pharmaceutical Applications of Membrane Sensors", CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida, 1992; *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1993, **24**, 1.
9. A. P. Gupta, H. Agarwal and G. L. Verma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 1910; H. Agarwal and S. Chandra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 2361; H. Agarwal, A. P. Gupta and G. L. Verma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 666.
10. S. H. Hoke, A. G. Collins and C. A. Reynolds, *Anal. Chem.*, 1979, **51**, 879; IUPAC, Analytical Chemistry Division, Commission on Analytical Nomenclature, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1995, **67**, 507.
11. H. E. Brookes and C. A. Johnson, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1955, **7**, 846.
12. C. Reetha, K. K. Aravindashan and C. Janardanan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 1438.
13. A. Craggs, G. J. Moody and J. D. R. Thomas, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1974, **51**, 561.